

DYNAMIC BEHAVIOR OF VIRGIN AND RECYCLED PP/EPR AND PP/EPDM/TALC MATERIALS FOR CAR BUMPERS

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Abstract: Our study deals with the recycling and strain rate effects on the dynamic mechanical behaviour of polymer composites. We particularly focus our study on high impact polypropylene and talc filled high impact polypropylene. Virgin specimens have been reprocessed (extruded) from 1 to 12 times in order to evaluate the degradation due to recycling. Dynamic compression tests have been performed for different strain rates. A comparison between experimental data obtained for both materials, virgin and recycled, have been carried out. These have permitted to quantify not only strain rate sensitivity but also the degradation of the mechanical properties after the recycling. These data have been used to propose a first modeling of the yield stress, which include strain rate effects, temperature effects and recycling effects. Preliminary results of our simulations have been compared with the experimental data for virgin (none recycled) materials only and good agreements have been found.

1. Introduction

The recycling of polymers for the automotive applications will impose recycling of used part as the shielding parts. Unlike metals which are easily recoverable and recyclable, plastics waste increase forces governments to legislate for the limitation of such waste by introducing the concept of isofunctional recycling [1]. Polypropylene and its compounds are the materials mostly encountered in a car (25%) [2]. The used materials in this study are composite polypropylene. On a one hand, several works [3-6] reported the strong influence of different heterogeneities (talc or rubber nodules) on the microstructure and on the mechanical behavior. Thus, this part won't be take into account in this paper. Only references will be reported when needed. On the other hand, The reprocessing effects on high impact polypropylene materials were partially studied [3-7]. Degradations induced by the ageing and the recycling of composite based

polypropylene were quantified under quasi-static loading by Bahlouli et al., Pessey et al. and Luda et al [8-13]. During multiple extrusion/crushing processes, the main result is that polymer chain scission induces the degradation of the mechanical properties.

The purpose of this paper is to quantify the effect of the recycling process by analysing the mechanical response for two high impact polypropylenes. These materials are classically used in automotive structures like bumpers. A detailed thermal, rheological, mechanical and morphological analysis has been performed on the recycled materials [14]. Thus, in order to quantify the degradation induced by the several reprocessing runs, tensile tests, dynamic compression tests using in a home made Hopkinson were carried out. The volume strain was also measured and used in our analyses as a damage indicator. In addition, a micromechanical modelling of the yield stress, based on the work of Richeton et al. [15] [16] was proposed for a wide range of strain rates and temperature. This modelling was developed using a multiscale approach to integrate the effect of elastomer and talc particles. Preliminary results of our simulations and comparison to the experimental results will be presented.

2. Materials and experiments

In order to use recycled polymers for structural part of cars, recycling effects on quasistatic to high strain rates response for different temperatures of composite based polypropylene were studied in this paper. The materials used in this study are two commercial grades, referenced by SABIC® PP, grade 108MF97 and SABIC® PPcompound, grade 7510. They differ from their percentage of elastomeric nodules (22% of EPR in 108MF97, 20% of EPDM in 7510) and from their percentage of talc

(0.5% in 108MF97, 12% in 7510). Moulded sheets were provided by the LRMP (University of St-Etienne). To reproduce the recycling process, six cycles of extrusion were performed in the extrusion BiscREW machine with a flow of 10kg/h at temperature of 230°C. Different dynamic compression tests were performed for different strain rates and temperatures on a home made Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB) (fig.1 to 3). The experimental stress strain curves of the recycled polymers were always below the curves obtained for the virgin polymers.

Fig.1. Strain rate and recycling sensibility of the stress strain curve for the 108MF97

Fig.2. Strain rate sensibility of the yield stress for the 108MF97.

Fig.3. Strain rate sensibility of the elastic modulus for the 108MF97.

Fig.4. Recycling effects on the stress strain curve for the 7510

3. Micromechanical modelling of the yield stress

Instead of considering the entire process as a whole, Fotheringham and Cherry [17] considered the individual segment motions as separate events and built a model based on n cooperative jumps.

The resulting cooperative model is expressed as:

$$\frac{\sigma_{eff}}{T} = \frac{k}{V} \sinh^{-1} \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{\dot{\epsilon}_0 \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta H}{kT}\right)} \right)^{1/n} \quad (2)$$

where n describes the cooperative character of the yield process. Richeton et al. [15-16] extended the cooperative model to amorphous polymers above the glass transition temperature and showed that the yield behavior of amorphous polymers can be correlated to secondary relaxations. The expressions of the cooperative model below and above the glass transition temperature are given by :

$$\frac{\sigma_y}{T} = \frac{\sigma_i(0) - m \cdot T}{T} + \frac{2k}{V} \sinh^{-1} \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{\epsilon_0 \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta H_\beta}{kT}\right)} \right)^{1/n}$$

for $T < T_g$ (1)

$$\frac{\sigma_y}{T} = \frac{2k}{V} \sinh^{-1} \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{\epsilon_0 \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta H_\beta}{kT}\right) \exp\left(\frac{\ln 10 \times c_1^g (T - T_g)}{c_2^g + T - T_g}\right)} \right)^{1/n}$$

for $T \geq T_g$ (2)

Here ΔH_β is the β activation energy, c_1^g and c_2^g are the WLF parameters; T_g is the glass transition; $\sigma_i(0)$ is the internal stress at 0K and m is a material parameter roughly equal to $\sigma_i(0)/T_g$ in the case of amorphous polymers.

This cooperative model was recently extended to predict the yield stress of the semi-crystalline polymers [18] and nanocomposites [19]. For semi crystalline polymers and nanocomposites, the main changes in the equations 1 and 2 concern the free volume and the activation energy. In order to take into account the multicomponent character of the composites and semi crystalline polymers, these two quantities are calculated by a multiscale modeling of the effective activation parameters (Takayanagi model, 1963). On figure 5, comparison with modelling and experimental master curve is presented for the 108MF97. A good correlation is found.

4. Conclusion

In this work, the recycling and the strain rate effects on the dynamic behavior of two polymer based composites have been obtain. A first model of the

dynamic yield stress has been proposed and a good correlation has been obtained.

Fig.5. Modeling of the master curve for the 108MF97

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